

Oxidative stress as a key factor in the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative diseases: molecular mechanisms and protection pathways – Review

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Abstract

Aging is the main risk factor in neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), Huntington's disease (HD), and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). It has been widely demonstrated that oxidative stress contributes to their pathogenesis during aging due to increased production of oxidative species and the failure of antioxidant defenses.

It is well known that reactive oxygen species (ROS) are constantly produced in aerobic organisms. However, excessive generation of ROS or dysfunction of the antioxidant system causes oxidative stress. The elevated oxygen demand of the brain is one of the common reasons for its high vulnerability to the effects of ROS. A number of studies have demonstrated the central role of oxidative stress in the recurrent pathophysiology of neurodegenerative diseases.

The current review aims to outline and summarize current knowledge on the influence of oxidative stress mechanisms in neurodegenerative diseases.

Keywords

amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, Huntington's disease, neurodegenerative diseases, Nrf2, oxidative stress, reactive oxygen species

Introduction

Oxidative stress (OS) is an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and their elimination by the antioxidant system (Aranda-Rivera et al. 2022).

ROS and oxidative stress

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) is a generic term that defines a wide variety of oxidant molecules with vastly different properties and biological functions that range from

signaling to causing cell damage (Sies et al. 2022). ROS production is tightly regulated by redox signaling and sensing mechanisms. ROS signaling may participate in normal physiological processes or contribute to maladaptive responses that result in metabolic dysfunction and inflammatory signaling, depending on the ROS source, cell type, and tissue environment. The two major sources of ROS inside the cell are nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase (NOX) enzymes and the mitochondria (Masenga et al. 2023; Palma et al. 2024). Based on their chemical features, ROS can be divided into two classes: free radicals and non-radicals. Free radicals usually refer to ROS containing one unpaired reactive electron in the outer orbit and belong to one-electron oxidants. The major free radicals include nitric oxide (NO•), superoxide radical anion (O₂•⁻), hydroxyl radical (OH•), carbonate radical anion (CO₃•⁻), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂•), and alkoxy/alkyl peroxy (RO•/ROO•). Non-free radicals do not contain an unpaired electron and belong to two-electron oxidants. Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), peroxynitrite (ONOO⁻)/peroxynitrous acid (ONOOH), and hypochlorous acid (HOCl) are the major non-radical species (Zhang et al. 2019; Chianese and Pierantoni 2021; Okoye et al. 2023).

Superoxide anion

The superoxide anion O₂•⁻ is a reduced form of molecular oxygen O₂, consisting of two oxygen atoms with 17 electrons and a negative electrical charge. It is formed when an oxygen molecule acquires an electron. Superoxide is the first species produced in the respiratory chain by the reduction of oxygen through electron transfer and is one of the first species generated by various cellular systems. The initial formation of O₂•⁻ triggers a cascade of ROS, some of which, such as H₂O₂, behave as key molecules in cell signaling, whereas others, such as HO•, are damaging. O₂•⁻ is formed in all living aerobic organisms and can act as a signaling agent, a toxic species, or a harmless intermediate that spontaneously decomposes. Its levels are limited *in vivo* by two different types of enzymes: superoxide reductase (SOR) and superoxide dismutase (SOD). O₂•⁻ is a relatively small anion, highly soluble in water, where it is solvated by four water molecules strongly bound by hydrogen bonds, and reacts with a proton or proton donor to form HO₂• (Jie et al. 2022; Andrés et al. 2023).

Hydroxyl radical

The hydroxyl radical (•OH) is a powerful oxidant that is produced in a wide range of environments via the Fenton reaction (1):

The reactants are formed from the reduction of Fe³⁺ and O₂. The hydroxyl radical can also be produced from the superoxide anion and hydrogen peroxide via the Haber–Weiss reaction (Haber and Weiss 1932). The reaction is mainly based on the decomposition of released cellular hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) through a chain reaction following the steps of initiation (1), propagation (2 and 3), and termination (4) (Koppenol 2001).

The initiation step is based on the Fenton reaction:

The propagation follows by two successive steps, including:

And the termination occurs at scavenging the hydroxyl radical by a ferrous ion:

A strong pH dependency is observed in the Haber–Weiss reaction, related to the solubility of the two necessary ionic components, Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺, in solution, which is highly pH dependent. Thus, the conclusion drawn determines the requirement of sufficiently acidic conditions. In addition, the pH value also directly influences the acid–base dissociation equilibrium involving the hydroperoxyl and the superoxide radicals (pKa = 4.7) (Bielski 1978). This radical (HO•) degrades organic compounds, which makes it harmful if produced in excess and in close proximity to cells. Such oxidative stress reactions can have a range of adverse effects (Lyngsie et al. 2018; Zhao 2023).

Hydrogen peroxide

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is recognized as the major non-radical ROS. It is produced from O₂ mainly by NADPH oxidases in conjunction with superoxide dismutases, by the mitochondrial electron transport chain, and by numerous other enzymes. H₂O₂ is a strong two-electron oxidant, but its high activation energy confines its reactivity to a few biological targets. H₂O₂ is relatively stable. It reacts very slowly with glutathione, cysteine, and methionine, but its reactivity toward cysteine in specific proteins can increase greatly depending on the particular protein structure and environment, providing a basis for the selectivity and specificity of H₂O₂ in redox signaling. H₂O₂ reacts moderately with iron–sulfur (Fe–S) clusters and loosely bound metals. H₂O₂ can react with CO₂/bicarbonate to form peroxymonocarbonate (HCO₄⁻), an oxidant that reacts with biological targets with a second-order rate constant about two to three orders of magnitude greater than that for H₂O₂. *In vivo* levels of H₂O₂ are limited by the enzymes glutathione peroxidase, peroxiredoxin, and catalase. H₂O₂ is a source for production of the hydroxyl radical via Fenton and Haber–Weiss reactions (Sies and Jones 2020, Wang et al. 2024).

Factors causing oxidative stress

ROS can be provided from extracellular or intracellular sources. Extracellular sources include ultraviolet (UV) light, ionizing radiation, heavy or transition metals, and others. In contrast, intracellular sources comprise mitochondria, peroxisomes, endoplasmic reticulum, and

nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen oxidases (NOXs) (Aranda-Rivera et al. 2022). The main factors associated with oxidative stress are:

Ultraviolet radiation

Ultraviolet radiation, predominantly UVB (290–320 nm wavelength), causes massive production of photooxidative damage by reactive oxygen species (ROS), including hydroxyl radicals, superoxide anions, singlet oxygen, and hydrogen peroxide in anion-exposed cells. During the generation of ROS from UV irradiation, photons are absorbed by endogenous photosensitizer molecules, which react with oxygen, resulting in increases of various free radicals, causing damage to the exposed cells (Ivanov et al. 2018; Samviel et al. 2020).

Ionizing radiation

Ionizing radiation, absorbed by tissues and cells, affects their functioning and structure to various extents, depending on the dose and type of radiation. In affected cells, ROS are generated mainly through the radiolysis of water molecules (decay by the action of radiation quanta) or the excitation of water molecules and their decay. Ionizing radiation can also indirectly influence oxidative–antioxidant homeostasis by damaging different biomolecules. The altered molecules, such as DNA or proteins responsible for stabilizing the DNA structure, become more susceptible to damage caused by ROS. In addition, antioxidants or genes encoding for enzymatic antioxidants can be damaged, which directly increases oxidative stress. A meta-analysis based on 41 studies concerning various biological matrices proved that IR, even at low doses, generates ROS (Nuszkiewicz et al. 2020).

Heavy metals

Among the heavy metals/metalloids, chromium (Cr), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), and lead (Pb) are considered priority hazards for public health due to their presence in different environmental compartments, ubiquitous human exposure, and severe toxicity even at a low level. Direct or indirect ROS generation, reduced glutathione (GSH) depletion, and inhibition of the activity of antioxidant defense enzymes are well-known mechanisms for metal-induced toxicities. The involvement of different signaling pathways in heavy metal-induced pathological processes has been documented (Paithankar et al. 2021).

Pesticides

Pesticide-induced oxidative stress is caused by both reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), which are associated with several diseases, including cancer, inflammation, and cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases. The low molecular weight and high lipophilicity of pesticides increase their absorption and toxicity level. Organophosphate and carbamate pesticides produce their effects through the inhibition of carboxyl ester hydrolases, in particular acetylcholinesterase, which leads to acetylcholine accumulation. Moreover, some studies have suggested that acetylcholinesterase enzyme inhibition is associated with the increase in ROS in agri-

cultural workers exposed to organophosphate pesticides and bipyridyl herbicides. Oxidative stress can be induced by an increase in lipid peroxidation and a decrease in antioxidant capacity (Freyre et al. 2021; Sule et al. 2022).

Air pollution

Air pollution is a complex mixture of gases and particles derived from both human activity (transport and industry) and natural sources (windblown dust, sea-salt spray, and volatile organic compound emissions from plants). It includes solid and liquid particles suspended in the air. The capacity of inhaled particulate matter and pollutant gases to cause oxidative stress is a primary pathway leading to the observed diseases seen in exposed populations. Ozone is a powerful oxidant, and nitrogen dioxide is a free radical. Airborne particles contain a range of components that are either direct redox catalysts (Fe, Cu, Ni, quinones) or can be metabolized to reactive electrophiles *in vivo* (Mudway et al. 2020; Leni et al. 2020; Dondi et al. 2023).

Endogenous antioxidant system

To control ROS, the body uses several antioxidant mechanisms, including enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants. Non-enzymatic low-molecular-weight antioxidant compounds include cellular glutathione, vitamins C and E, β -carotene, polyphenols, and uric acid. Antioxidant enzymes include superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione reductase, and glutathione peroxidase, among others (Andrés et al. 2023).

Superoxide dismutase

Superoxide dismutases (SODs) are a group of metalloenzymes that are found in all kingdoms of life. SODs form the front line of defense against reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated injury (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Ribbon diagram of a human superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2) tetramer. Manganese ions are shown in violet. Created using PyMOL (<http://www.pymol.org>) and GIMP. Optimized using OptiPNG (Borgstahl et al. 1996).

These proteins catalyze the dismutation of the superoxide anion free radical ($O_2^{\cdot -}$) into molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and decrease the $O_2^{\cdot -}$ level, which damages the cells at excessive concentration. This reaction is accompanied by alternate oxidation–reduction of metal ions present in the active site of SODs. Based on the metal cofactors present in the active sites, SODs can be classified into four distinct groups: copper–zinc SOD (Cu, Zn-SOD), iron SOD (Fe-SOD), manganese SOD (Mn-SOD), and nickel SOD (Ni-SOD) (Younus 2018, Rosa et al. 2021, Zheng et al. 2023).

Catalase

Catalase (CAT) is one of the most important antioxidant enzymes. It is present in almost all aerobic organisms (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Ribbon diagram of a human catalase (Jawahar Swaminathan and MSD staff at the European Bioinformatics Institute – https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/static/entry/7cat_deposited_chain_front_image-800x800.png, displayed on <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/entry/pdb/7cat>).

Catalase breaks down two hydrogen peroxide molecules into one molecule of oxygen and two molecules of water in a two-step reaction (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the mechanism of action of human catalase.

The first step of the reaction mechanism involves the formation of a spectroscopically distinct intermediate, compound I, which is a covalent oxoferryl species ($FeI-$

VO) having a porphyrin π -cation radical, through the reduction of one hydrogen peroxide molecule.

In the second step of the reaction, compound I is reduced through redox reactions by a two-electron transfer from an electron donor (the second molecule of hydrogen peroxide) to produce the free enzyme, oxygen, and water (Nandi et al. 2019; Anwar et al. 2024).

Glutathione peroxidase

Glutathione peroxidases (GPXs) constitute a family of phylogenetically related selenoprotein oxidoreductases observed in all living organisms (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Ribbon diagram of a human glutathione peroxidase.

This family is a central component of the cellular antioxidant defense system (Weaver and Skouta 2022). The main reaction that GPX catalyzes is:

where GSH represents reduced glutathione and GS–SG represents the oxidized form of glutathione – glutathione

disulfide. The mechanism of action of GPX involves two steps – an oxidation reaction followed by a reduction reaction (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Mechanism of glutathione peroxidase redox pathway (Pei et al. 2023).

The first step consists of the oxidation of the selenol of a selenocysteine residue in the reduced GPX enzyme by hydrogen peroxide:

The second step is a series of reductions of the oxidized GPX enzyme by a thiol-containing compound such as the reduced cofactor glutathione (GSH) (Flohé et al. 2022; Weaver and Skouta 2022):

Glutathione reductase

Glutathione reductase (GR) (Fig. 6) is a specific antioxidant enzyme that catalyzes oxidized glutathione (GSSG) to reduced glutathione (GSH) (Fig. 7):

Figure 6. Ribbon diagram of a human glutathione reductase.

Figure 7. Mechanism of glutathione reductase pathway.

GR enzyme maintains the cellular reduced GSH level and plays a central role in cell defense against reactive oxygen species (Ciftci et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2023).

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

6-OHDA	6-hydroxydopamine;
AD	Alzheimer's disease;
ALS	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis;
AMPK	AMP-activated protein kinase;
APAF	Apoptosis associated factors;
APOE	Apolipoprotein E;
APP	Amyloid precursor protein;
CAT	Catalase;
CNS	Central nervous system;
EpRE	Electrophile response element;
GPX	Glutathione peroxidase;
GR	Glutathione reductase;
GSH	Reduced form of glutathione;
GSSG	Oxidized form of glutathione;
HD	Huntington's disease;
MAPK	Mitogen activated protein kinases;
MPTP	1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine;
NMDARs	N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors;
NOS	Nitric oxide synthase;
PD	Parkinson's disease;
RNS	Reactive nitrogen species;
ROS	Reactive oxygen species;
SOD	Superoxide dismutase.

Role of oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases

The brain is especially sensitive to oxidative damage because of its high and specific metabolic activity. High consumption of oxygen, almost exclusive oxidative phosphorylation, no reserves of energy, high concentrations of lipids prone to peroxidation, and high levels of iron all act as pro-oxidants. Neuronal cells are, therefore, highly susceptible to metabolic/ischemic damage and associated oxidative stress (Jelinek et al. 2021; Domanskyi and Parla to 2022; Houldsworth 2024). Oxidative stress in the brain is one of the main factors in the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative diseases. Neurodegenerative diseases are a group of CNS diseases characterized by progressive loss of neuron cells, compromised motor or cognitive functions, and accumulation of abnormally aggregated proteins (Fig. 8) (Cenini et al. 2019; Teleanu et al. 2022).

As it is usually seen in the brain, where a neurotoxic effect is often the result of unbalanced production of a physiologically important element (i.e., “too much of a good thing”), several ROS play physiological roles when produced in a controlled way (Contestabile 2001). Thus, for instance, the superoxide radical ($\text{O}_2\bullet$), which is produced

Figure 8. Role of oxidative stress in the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative diseases.

in excess by activated microglia and damages neurons in chronic inflammatory states, may bear pathophysiological importance as a growth regulator, an intercellular diffusible signal, and a bacterial killer in acute infective states (Halliwell 1992; Contestabile 2000).

Cellular signals and mechanisms of neuronal death induced by ROS

Oxidative stress increases the risk of DNA and protein damage in the aging brain due to attenuation of antioxidant mechanisms. Mitochondria have been identified as a preferential site of accumulation of metabolic errors and structural damage during the process of cellular aging in many tissues, including the brain. Furthermore, oxidative stress has been involved in several neurodegenerative diseases for which aging may represent an additional risk factor. This is the case for Alzheimer's disease, Huntington's disease, Parkinson's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, schizophrenia, and prion disease (Contestabile 2001; Raber et al. 2023; Samarakoon et al. 2023; Wu et al. 2023). Neuronal death related to pathological conditions may be necrotic or apoptotic in nature, the former prevailing in acute injury while the latter is characteristic of chronic brain damage. While a characteristic feature of apoptosis was initially identified by its dependence on *de novo* RNA and protein synthesis, there is now a general consensus that apoptosis and necrosis are the two extreme ends of a functional continuum of cellular paths to death. The regulation, at the genetic and molecular level, of the cellular metabolic pathways leading to apoptosis has been well characterized in neural cells and appears to be relatively well conserved in different tissues and among different species (Contestabile 2001; Gupta et al. 2021; Mitoma et al. 2021; Mao et al. 2022).

A central element in several models of OS-related brain injury is represented by nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) activation (Fig. 9). This redox-sensitive transcription factor is activated by several ROS, including the hydroxyl radical, while hydroxyl radical scavengers or metal chelators inhibiting the conversion of hydrogen peroxide to hydroxyl radical inhibit its activation. NF- κ B, in the unstimulated condition, is present in the cell as an inactive complex

Figure 9. Ribbon diagram of nuclear factor NF- κ B subunit 2.

constituted of the P50/P65 dimer linked to the inhibitory protein I κ B.

Phosphorylation of the inhibitory protein results in its ubiquitination and proteasome-mediated degradation, releasing the active NF- κ B dimer, which translocates to the nucleus where it can regulate the transcription of several genes. A host of genes regulated by NF- κ B has been identified and includes cytokines; death and survival proteins such as those of the Bcl family, Myc, and p53; adhesion molecules; and enzymes involved in ROS generation, such as cyclooxygenase 2 and inducible NOS. Therefore, a vicious circle of ROS-induced ROS production may be triggered by NF- κ B activation. At the same time, damage to the blood-brain barrier can additionally contribute to brain injury (Contestabile 2001; Gao et al. 2021; Li et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2022).

Other cellular pathways activated by ROS have been suggested to contribute to brain damage. One of these pathways is related to a nuclear DNA repair enzyme, apurinic/apyrimidinic endonuclease (APE), whose expression is quickly decreased in neurons subjected to oxidative stress-based brain injuries (Hong et al. 2023; Yuan et al. 2025). In addition to directly altering DNA repair, APE levels are also implicated in the redox activation of the AP-1 transcription factor by altering its DNA-binding potency and, therefore, modifying the expression of a large number of other genes. The involvement of AP-1 as a mediator of cellular signals activated by ROS production is further confirmed by the increase in the levels of its monomeric components, c-Jun and c-Fos, as a consequence of hydroxyl radical generation in cerebellar granule cells *in vitro* (Nagesh et al. 2021; Oliveira et al. 2022). In addition to NF- κ B and AP-1, other transcription factors that share the property of being redox sensitive, such as EIK-1 and SP-1, may be implicated in the transduction of signals generated by ROS production in neurons. The strong potency of ROS in activating gene expression in nerve cells is demonstrated by recent experiments showing that both induction of oxidative stress and treatment with antioxi-

dants induce sizeable variations in the expression of several genes, many of which are directly or indirectly related to ROS metabolism (Joshi et al. 2022; Tsai et al. 2023). A further cellular signal induced by increased ROS generation in neurons is the one related to activation of some kinases, in particular those of the family of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), which in turn may regulate the activation states of several transcription factors. Finally, important signals are generated by ROS-mediated mitochondrial damage, which originate from cytochrome C release and proceed through other apoptosis-associated factors (APAF) and the activation of proteases belonging to the caspase family (Contestabile 2001; Singh et al. 2021; Behrouzi et al. 2022; Gravandi et al. 2023; Kohutova et al. 2023; Rios-Covian et al. 2023; Pranty et al. 2024).

Role of Nrf2 in defense against oxidative stress and neurodegenerative diseases

The phase II antioxidant response is considered the most important defense pathway present in cells. It is regulated by the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2 (NFE2)-related factor 2 (Nrf2) (Fig. 10), a member of the cap'n collar family of basic region–leucine zipper transcription factors.

Nrf2 is responsible for both constitutive and inducible expression of electrophile response element (EpRE)-reg-

Figure 10. Structure of the Neh1 domain of Nrf2; helices are displayed as ribbons (Brüschweiler et al. 2021).

ulated genes, such as NAD(P)H quinone oxidoreductase-1 (NQO1), heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1), thioredoxins (Trxs), glutathione S-transferase (GST), microsomal GSTs (mGST1 and mGST2), γ -glutamylcysteine synthetase (γ -GCS) modifier subunit (GCLm) and catalytic subunit (GCLc), glutathione reductase (GR), superoxide dismutase-1 (SOD1), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), and other phase I, II, and III enzymes that conjugate drug metabolites or xenobiotics (Buendia et al. 2016; Zgorzynska et al. 2021). Under normal conditions, the Nrf2–EpRE system keeps the Nrf2 protein at low levels. This is achieved by constitutive synthesis and degradation of Nrf2. The repressor protein Kelch-like ECH-associated protein-1 (Keap1), which is mainly present in the cytoplasm, tightly regulates this process. Keap1 binds to an E3 ubiquitin ligase complex (Rbx-1) via cullin-3, a protein adaptor. This complex promotes Nrf2 ubiquitination and 26S proteasome degradation. Keap1 is an excellent redox sensor of xenobiotics and oxidative stress inside the cells. It has three cysteine residues (Cys151, Cys273, and Cys288) that are crucial for Keap1-dependent ubiquitination of Nrf2 (Fahim et al. 2023; Ren et al. 2023). Under cellular stress, such as ROS or environmental chemicals, oxidative/electrophilic molecules modify cysteine residues of Keap1. These modifications result in conformational changes of Keap1 to release Nrf2. As a result, the cullin-3/Rbx-1-dependent polyubiquitination of Nrf2 assisted by Keap1 is blocked, Nrf2 is liberated, and it rapidly translocates into the nucleus. Once in the nucleus, Nrf2 heterodimerizes with small MAF or JUN proteins, and the complex binds to a cis-acting element present in the promoter of its target genes, called antioxidant response elements (AREs), also denominated electrophile response elements (EpREs) (Buendia et al. 2016; Zgorzynska et al. 2021; Uruno and Yamamoto 2023). This activation mechanism of Nrf2 under stress conditions is known as the “hinge and latch” model. Many described Nrf2 inducers as electrophilic compounds that react with cysteines present in Keap1 (Camiña and Penning 2022; Tossetta and Marzioni 2023). Nevertheless, recently different molecules have been described that are able to inhibit the protein–protein interaction between Keap1 and Nrf2. Moreover, the Nrf2 system is regulated by an autoregulatory loop. Nrf2 regulates the transcription of Keap1, cullin-3, and Rbx-1, and, in turn, Keap1/cullin-3/Rbx-1 degrades Nrf2. The Keap1 complex can also be imported into the nucleus, where it promotes the degradation of nuclear Nrf2. Further feedback systems appear to exist since Nrf2 activation induces proteasome expression and activity. It has been observed that Nrf2 activators increase the expression of genes encoding for the proteasome subunits 20S and 19S. As described above, oxidative damage, mitochondrial dysfunction, and chronic inflammatory status are common pathological pathways widely described in neurodegenerative diseases (Buendia et al. 2016; Uruno and Yamamoto 2023). The Nrf2–EpRE pathway acts as a sensor and regulator of oxidative stress, being tightly regulated under normal conditions. Compelling evidence suggests that this pathway is deregulated in neurodegenerative diseases and thus contributes to inten-

sifying the advance and severity of the diseases. Moreover, aging is one of the most common risk factors in neurodegenerative diseases. It has been widely demonstrated that oxidative stress augments during aging due to an increased production of oxidative species and the failure of antioxidant defenses. In this line, compelling data indicate that the ability of Nrf2 to activate the phase II antioxidant response declines with aging, thus contributing to an exacerbated status of oxidative stress. Different Nrf2 inducers have been studied for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases (Fig. 11) (Buendia et al. 2016; Cuadrado 2022; Saha et al. 2022; Suzen et al. 2022; Amoroso et al. 2023).

Figure 11. Role of Nrf2 in neuroprotection and prevention of neurodegenerative diseases.

The most common neurodegenerative diseases are Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), Huntington's disorders (HD), and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) (Rekatsina et al. 2020).

Oxidative stress and Alzheimer's disease (AD)

Alzheimer's disease is characterized by progressive loss of cognitive and behavioral deterioration, which leads to the impairment of daily and routine activities. It is one of the most prevalent neurodegenerative disorders, manifesting in 45 million people worldwide. Alzheimer's disease is manifested with the deposition of protein aggregates, extracellular amyloid plaques ($A\beta$), intracellular tau (τ) or neurofibrillary tangles, and loss of synaptic connections in specific regions of the brain (Singh et al. 2019). Numerous studies have documented mitochondrial dysfunction through the abnormal processing of ROS as an essential factor in AD pathogenesis. Similarly, the insertion of $A\beta$ as oligomers into the bilayer can lead to the development of ROS, thereby initiating lipid peroxidation of membranes, followed by intracellular protein and nucleic acid oxidation. It is also important to note that oxidative stress is linked to mitochondrial function, not only because mitochondria generate ROS, but also because ROS can cause deterioration of mitochondrial function (Misrani et al.

2021; Dhapola et al. 2024; Naik et al. 2025). The increased production of ROS molecules, including superoxide anion ($O_2\bullet^-$), hydroxyl radical (HO), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), in addition to poor antioxidant status, exacerbates the pathoprogession of AD. ROS molecules are generated as the by-products of multiple enzymatic reactions in several subcellular organelles and compartments, including mitochondria, endoplasmic reticulum (ER), peroxisome, and cytoplasm. Specific enzymes in these subcellular organelles, such as NAD(P)H oxidase (NOX), nitric oxide synthase (NOS), cyclooxygenase (COX), and xanthine oxidase (XO), produce intracellular ROS. ROS are produced via different signaling cascades, including the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B), and the mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathways (Ionescu-Tucker and Cotman 2021; Sharma and Kim 2021; Beura et al. 2022). ROS causes damage to the blood-brain barrier, which regulates the transit of chemicals between the blood and the brain. This can cause harmful compounds to build up in the brain, contributing to the progression of AD. One possible treatment strategy for AD is to tackle oxidative stress (Jurcău et al. 2022; Aran and Singh 2023). Beta-amyloid has also been shown to cause mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress. This increases the production of ROS, which damages DNA, proteins, and lipids, contributing to neuronal dysfunction and death. Furthermore, dysfunctional mitochondria can accelerate the pathological process by exacerbating tau phosphorylation, another hallmark of AD (Alqahtani et al. 2023). Several studies have indicated that neuroinflammation also plays a critical role in AD pathogenesis. Neuroinflammation is expressed by the activation of microglial cells and astrocytes, which release and respond to a wide variety of chemokines and pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) and interleukin (IL)-1 β and IL-6) mediating innate immune responses, as well as by the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) boosting oxidative stress. Hence, the treatment of neuroinflammation and oxidative stress appears to be of primary importance in alleviating AD pathology (Decandia et al. 2023). The amyloid cascade hypothesis suggests that the hydrolysate of amyloid precursor protein (APP), the $A\beta$ peptide, is a key factor that leads to AD. Genetic studies show that the development of $A\beta$ pathology is associated with AD genes (e.g., mutations in presenilin 1 (PSEN1), presenilin 2 (PSEN2), and apolipoprotein E (APOE)). APP is a type of single-pass transmembrane protein that forms the $A\beta$ peptide via two different processing pathways (the amyloid pathway and the nonamyloid pathway). $A\beta$ peptides tend to aggregate to form unstable secondary or tertiary structures, which subsequently form $A\beta$ oligomers under external factors such as temperature and pH (Orobets and Karamyshev 2023; Yang et al. 2023). In the amyloid pathway, APP is cleaved by β -secretase (BACE1) and γ -secretase to produce $A\beta$ 1-40/42 peptides, which are then transported to the extracellular space via receptors, where they aggregate to form $A\beta$ oligomers. $A\beta$ oligomers exert potent cytotoxicity. On one hand, $A\beta$ oligomers destroy the activity

of NMDA receptors, resulting in the generation of extracellular ROS and excessive calcium influx into neurons, eventually causing mitochondrial dysfunction (Roda et al. 2022; Ghosh et al. 2023). On the other hand, aggregation of A β oligomers produces A β fibers and extracellular SPs, leading to oxidative stress and promoting cell apoptosis (Bai et al. 2022). An important AD disease modifier is apolipoprotein E (APOE), which encodes a secreted, lipid-shuttling protein highly expressed in the brain. The ϵ 4 allele of APOE (APOE4) is the most common known genetic risk factor for AD (Fig. 12).

Figure 12. Schematic representation of the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease.

Furthermore, the ϵ 2 allele (APOE2) seems neuroprotective against AD (Brookhouser et al. 2021; Serrano-Pozo et al. 2021). Patients carrying the AD risk allele APOE4 may have higher amounts of O₂-lipids than individuals carrying other APOE alleles. These O₂-lipids are transferred to glia, where they form lipid droplets (LDs). LDs typically involve a phospholipid monolayer surrounding neutral lipids (e.g., triacylglycerides, cholesterol). O₂-lipid production in neurons involves ROS-induced c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) activation and subsequent activation and phosphorylation of a transcription factor that regulates lipid biosynthesis, sterol regulatory element binding protein (SREBP). This is an important mechanism in the pathophysiology of AD (Goodman and Bellen 2022).

Oxidative stress and Parkinson's disease (PD)

PD is a common progressive neurodegenerative disorder. PD is primarily characterized by degeneration of dopamine neurons in the *substantia nigra pars compacta* (SNpc) and their projections to the *corpus striatum*. Dopamine neuron loss leads to the manifestation of PD motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, resting tremor, postural instability, and rigidity (Church 2021; Pagonabarraga et al. 2021). Additionally, PD patients exhibit a broad range of non-motor symptoms, such as depression, sleep disorders, and dementia. Many of them precede the appearance of motor symptoms and worsen with progression of PD (Gupta and Shukla 2021; Kumaresan and Khan 2021). PD is the second most common cause of neurodegeneration

(Konovalova et al. 2019; Yan et al. 2021). The etiological factors of PD have not been clearly elucidated, but some cases of PD have been reported to be associated with metal poisoning, cerebrospinal meningitis, and genetic factors. Most (>90%) of PD cases are related to environmental exposures, with heritable factors accounting for only 5–10% of PD cases. These findings indicate that environmental factors play a significant role in the etiology of PD (Pyatha et al. 2022). Oxidative stress is one of the main factors behind neurodegeneration in PD. ROS activate microglia and astrocytes, causing the ongoing release of proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines analogous to the systemic, low-grade inflammation that occurs secondary to malignancy (Copas et al. 2021; Takahashi and Mashima 2022). ROS also play a crucial role in the differentiation of neurons by influencing the multiplication of brain progenitors and epigenetics (Fig. 13). ROS inhibit sodium currents needed for action potentials via oxidation of thiol groups. The opening of voltage-gated calcium channels is enhanced by ROS (Aborode et al. 2022; Dirks and Bologna 2022; Tchekalarova and Tzoneva 2023).

Figure 13. Schematic representation of the pathophysiology of Parkinson's disease.

Dopaminergic neurons tend to contain large amounts of ROS, derived from the enzymatic and nonenzymatic metabolism of dopamine (Nunes and Laranjinha 2021; Xu and Yang 2022). Consequently, they are more sensitive to various stress factors than other neurons. Dopamine may be catabolized by monoamine oxidase (MAO), a molecule bound to the outer mitochondrial membrane, in a process that generates H₂O₂ as a by-product (Cataldi et al. 2021; Dai et al. 2023). In addition, dopamine oxidation may occur spontaneously in the presence of iron, generating 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA), which is subsequently transformed into a reactive electrophilic molecule, p-quinone, in the presence of oxygen (Kostrzewa 2022; Prates-Rodrigues et al. 2025). Dopamine can also be oxidized to dopamine-quinone (DAQ), a molecule whose toxic effects are derived from its reaction with cysteine sulfhydryl groups. DAQ has been shown to affect the

cell's ability to sequester ROS by reacting with Cys-106 of the neuroprotective protein DJ-1 (Latif et al. 2021; Hurben and Tretyakova 2022). In *nigral* neurons not affected by PD, DJ-1 protein is mostly localized to the cytoplasm; however, when exposed to high levels of ROS, it is oxidized to the Cys-SO₂H form and translocated to the mitochondria and the nucleus. DJ-1 removes ROS with lower efficiency than other enzymes involved in oxidoreductive homeostasis (e.g., catalase), suggesting that it may instead act as an oxidative stress sensor by modulating signaling pathways and the expression of specific genes (Buneeva and Medvedev 2021; Skou et al. 2024). Increased levels of DJ-1 induce GSH synthesis, protecting dopamine neurons from the harmful effects of H₂O₂ and 6-OHDA. 6-OHDA, a substance typically elevated in animal models of PD, accumulates in *nigral* neurons, leading to various types of mitochondrial dysfunction, such as inhibition of respiratory chain function or a decrease in membrane potential (Mogensen et al. 2023; Lv et al. 2025). Further, it has been shown that elevated levels of ROS cause increased binding of DJ-1 to mitochondrial complex I, enhancing activity of NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase and, ultimately, the entire respiratory chain (Dorszewska et al. 2021; Chakrabarti and Bisaglia 2023; Zhou et al. 2023). Exposure to dopaminergic neurotoxins can trigger PD-related pathology. The first definite proof came from the early 1980s when a small number of humans inadvertently exposed themselves intravenously to 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP), a contaminant in illicit preparations of a potent synthetic opioid, which led to the development of all the classic PD motor symptoms. Postmortem brain analyses of some of these patients showed localized neurodegeneration in the SNpc with absent Lewy body pathology and loss of dopaminergic arborization in the striatum, along with undetectable neuronal loss in other brain regions typical in PD, such as the locus coeruleus (Fan et al. 2021; Mustapha and Taib 2021). These patients also displayed inflammatory glial activation at the time of death, supporting perpetuating neurodegeneration and inflammation years after MPTP exposure. Further studies in MPTP-intoxicated primates and mice confirmed the specificity of the neurotoxin toward the nigrostriatal circuit, where it causes damage in a similar pattern as observed in PD, characterized by preferential loss of dopaminergic terminals in the putamen compared to the caudate nucleus of the striatum, followed by increased loss of putamen-innervating neurons in the ventral lateral portions of the SNpc (AlShimemeri et al. 2021; Bagwell and Larsen 2024). Moreover, MPTP induces greater dopaminergic neurodegeneration in the SNpc than in dopaminergic neurons of the neighboring ventral tegmental area (VTA) that project to the caudate nucleus, a characteristic also observed in PD (Dionísio et al. 2021). Nitrosative stress is also an important factor in the pathophysiology of PD. Nitrosative stress results primarily from the overproduction of nitrogen-based free radicals: nitric oxide (NO⁻) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂⁻). These atoms possess unbalanced valence electrons and are therefore highly reactive and prone to filling their outer valence shells with

other atoms or molecules (Lacerus and Korniyakova 2022; Üremiş and Üremiş 2025). This can lead to the production of secondary free radicals such as peroxyne (ONOO⁻) and hydroxide anion (OH⁻), as well as toxic non-radicals such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), dinitrogen dioxide (N₂O₂), and nitrous acid (HNO₂) (Marí and Colell 2021; Tripodi et al. 2025). PD patients have elevated reactive nitrogen species (RNS), as indicated by increased levels of nitrite/nitrate in cerebrospinal fluid and blood. More specifically, it has been reported that white blood cell neutrophils in PD have higher expression of nNOS and an increased ability to produce excess NO. In a healthy system, NO has been ascribed a role in regulating mitochondrial function (Jarosiewicz and Morrell 2021; Kalyanaraman et al. 2024). In isolated synaptosomes, low levels of NO compete with oxygen to inhibit or activate cytochrome C, respectively. Since mitochondria cluster in regions where the demand for ATP is heightened, such as the synapse, it is possible that NO regulates mitochondrial oxygen consumption in order to maintain ATP supply. This regulation would be particularly important in the context of substantia-nigral dopaminergic neurons given their complex arborization and pace-making activity (Fonseca-Ornelas et al. 2021; Kostadinova et al. 2023). Moreover, substantia-nigral dopaminergic neurons have fast-spiking Ca²⁺ transients that increase the intracellular concentration of Ca²⁺, which is subsequently buffered, in part, by mitochondria. Not only does this put mitochondria at risk for Ca²⁺ overload leading to excitotoxicity and apoptosis, but Ca²⁺ that is not buffered may further stimulate neuronal nitric oxide synthase (nNOS)-generated NO. Together, mitochondrial NO reacts with superoxide produced by mitochondria to promote the production of the highly toxic ONOO⁻ (Vastegani et al. 2023; Bastioli et al. 2024). Studies have shown that ONOO⁻ can impair mitochondrial ATP synthesis through inhibition of mitochondrial respiratory complexes, mitochondrial depolarization, and detoxifying enzymes, in addition to promoting mitophagy. Many mitochondrial-related proteins are reported to be S-nitrosylated, both endogenously and in response to stimuli. The S-nitrosylation of the mitochondrial chaperone protein PHB has been shown to be neuroprotective against stress evoked by oxygen and glucose deprivation. However, PHB expression is reportedly reduced in PD patient brains, suggesting PD neurons are more susceptible to this stress. In PD patient brain tissue and cellular models of PD, S-nitrosylation of peroxiredoxin (PrxII) decreases peroxidase activity, causing H₂O₂ to accumulate, exacerbating oxidative stress (Stykel and Ryan 2022).

Oxidative stress and Huntington's disease (HD)

Huntington's disease is a genetically inherited, progressive neurodegenerative disease characterized by motor (most notably chorea), cognitive, and psychiatric anomalies (Medina et al. 2022; Tabrizi et al. 2022). This disease causes damage in the striatum, cerebral cortex, and basal ganglia, but the striatum is the first area to be affected (Sawant

et al. 2021; Islam et al. 2024). HD has an estimated prevalence of 1/10,000 to 1/20,000 people in the Caucasian population (Andhale and Shrivastava 2022). Due to its typically mid-life onset, autosomal dominant inheritance, and disturbing symptoms, HD inflicts devastating effects on the families of patients (Moghaddam et al. 2021). The pathogenic mechanisms of HD neurodegeneration remain elusive, hampering the development of new effective therapeutics. Although mitochondrial bioenergetic dysfunction and oxidative stress have been proposed to play a significant role, the exact mechanisms are not fully known (Brondani et al. 2023). Patients with HD have dendritic fluctuations in the basal ganglia and spiny neurons with reduced spine density in brain regions. Furthermore, brain imaging studies in HD patients and controls suggest that alterations in the cortico-striatal connection may contribute to depression and functional impairments. Neuronal cell loss in the striatum causes neurodegeneration, which is an important hallmark of HD (Trovato et al. 2022; Mahdi et al. 2023). Inflammation induced by microglial activation plays a critical role in neurodegeneration, such as seen in HD. Inflammatory mediator-induced neurodegeneration is triggered in part by prolonged and uncontrolled stimulation of microglia, as well as the enormous synthesis of inflammatory cytokines (Bin-Jumah et al. 2022). It is known that the administration of 3-nitropropionic acid (3-NP) to rodents causes striatal lesions that closely mimic the neuropathological and behavioral changes observed in HD patients and has been widely used as a valuable model of Huntington's disease (Ibrahim and Rasheed 2022; Lum et al. 2023). 3-NP is a potent inhibitor of succinate dehydrogenase, leading to alterations in mitochondrial bioenergetics, including reduced activities of respiratory chain complexes and citric acid cycle enzymes (Sharma et al. 2021; Upadhayay et al. 2023). Furthermore, the electron leakage secondary to respiratory chain dysfunction induced by 3-NP can be the source of reactive oxygen species generation, decreased antioxidant defenses, and the induction of oxidative cellular damage such as lipid peroxidation and protein and DNA damage, potentially inducing oxidative stress (Brondani et al. 2023). Oxidative stress plays a major role in HD pathology. In particular, neurons are extremely susceptible to oxidative damage (Sienes-Bailo et al. 2022; Jomova et al. 2025). Medium spiny neurons (MSNs) from the striatum exhibit, among all, greater vulnerability to toxic protein accumulation and its subsequent effects. The cause of MSNs' sensitivity relies on extrasynaptic glutamatergic signaling. Normally, the release of glutamate from neuronal synapses activates N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) that induce Ca^{2+} uptake, promoting neuronal plasticity and survival (Le Cann et al. 2021; Lebouc et al. 2025). In HD pathology, mutant huntingtin protein (mHtt) is responsible for the imbalance between synaptic and extrasynaptic NMDAR signaling, impairing the neuroprotective cascade related to cyclic AMP response element-binding protein (CREB) and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha (PGC-1 α) (Jarosińska and Rüdiger 2021; Sap et al. 2023). In this context, the deregulation of

PGC-1 α expression leads to reduced expression of antioxidants such as superoxide dismutase 1 and 2 (SOD1 and SOD2) as well as glutathione peroxidase 1 (GPx1), promoting oxidative stress and cell death (Pogoda et al. 2021; Panes et al. 2022). However, NMDARs are also involved in other mechanisms related to oxidative stress in mHtt-expressing neurons. For instance, NMDARs mediate Ca^{2+} mitochondrial uptake caused by mHtt interactions with mitochondria, stimulating production of ROS and damaging mitochondrial DNA. The impaired calcium signaling derived from mHtt interactions with mitochondria has detrimental effects on organelle dynamics. Damaged mitochondria play a crucial role in amplifying oxidative stress, but the endoplasmic reticulum, the ubiquitin-proteasome system, and autophagy are also involved. As already mentioned above, mHtt can alter these systems, causing oxidative stress, higher levels of metal ions, and impaired protein homeostasis (Fig. 14) (D'Egidio et al. 2023; Song et al. 2023; Beltrán et al. 2025).

Figure 14. Schematic representation of the pathophysiology of Huntington's disease.

The AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) also plays an important role in the pathology of HD. AMPK is an energy sensor that sustains cellular energy homeostasis by regulating downstream target genes. AMPK is a heterotrimeric complex composed of α , β , and γ subunits. AMPK can be activated by cAMP-dependent kinase, calmodulin-dependent protein kinase, liver kinase B1 (LKB1), and Ca^{2+} /calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II. The substrates of AMPK are involved in energy metabolism and different cellular processes. AMPK activation increases ROS formation, subsequently causing mitochondrial damage and apoptosis. The roles and regulation of AMPK in HD pathogenesis, including oxidative stress and DNA damage, have been investigated. AMPK activation occurs in striatal neurons of R6/2 mice and in patients with HD (Hua et al. 2022).

Oxidative stress and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS)

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis is a neurodegenerative disease characterized by progressive loss of motor neurons in the anterior horn of the spinal cord, leading to muscle weakness, wasting, and spasticity (Cenini et al. 2019). The most common form of ALS is sporadic (sALS), with no

known etiology, accounting for nearly 90–95% of all cases, while the remaining 5–10% of cases are inherited (familial ALS–fALS) and frequently associated with an earlier age of onset (Barberio et al. 2023; Shahim et al. 2024). Although the causes of sALS are still unknown, the disease has been associated with different risk factors, including age, smoking, body mass index, level of physical fitness, and occupational and environmental exposures to chemicals, pesticides, metals, and electromagnetic fields. However, as none of these external parameters are considered direct factors triggering the development of this disease, it is believed that there are individual susceptibility factors that, coupled with external environmental exposures, lead to the development of ALS (Feldman et al. 2022; Newell et al. 2022). Over 50 disease-modifying genes have been described in ALS; mutations in chromosome 9 open reading frame 72 (C9orf72), $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Zn}^{2+}$ superoxide dismutase type-1 (SOD-1), TAR DNA-binding (TARDBP), and fused in sarcoma (FUS) are among the most prevalent ones (Cunha-Oliveira et al. 2020). Oxidative stress plays a crucial role in motor neuron death in the pathophysiology of ALS. Increased ROS levels lead to the formation of other reactive species, such as RNS, due to O_2^- interacting with nitric oxide to form peroxynitrite (ONOO^-). Moreover, in addition to ROS and RNS, mitochondria produce reactive sulfur species (RSS), which are also highly reactive (Djordjevic et al. 2023; Shibata et al. 2025). Free oxygen radicals progressively damage proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, resulting in inefficient cellular processes, inflammation, and cell death (Hemerková and Vališ 2021; Sanghai and Tranmer 2021). Mitochondrial internal components and mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA), in particular, are highly susceptible to oxidative stress-induced damage, eventually hindering normal mitochondrial bioenergetics and increasing ROS production and oxidative stress (Motaitianu et al. 2022; Petrozziello et al. 2022; López-Pingarrón et al. 2023). Aberrant protein aggregation, including SOD-1 and transactive response DNA/RNA binding protein of 43 kDa (TDP-43), is the main pathological hallmark of familial and sporadic ALS (Duranti and Villa 2022; Wang and Zeng 2024). Aberrant protein aggregation is induced by oxidative stress, and conversely, oxidative stress is induced by aberrant protein aggregation. SOD-1 is localized in the cytosol, nucleus, peroxisomes, and mitochondria. As SOD-1 plays an important role in the antioxidant defense of the cell by converting O_2^\bullet to O_2 and H_2O_2 , the absence of SOD-1 causes an increase in oxidative stress. In ALS patients, more than 170 mutations have been identified, and aberrant aggregation of SOD-1 exists in spinal motor neurons from patients with sporadic and familial ALS (Hosaka et al. 2021; Goutman et al. 2022). Neuroinflammation, characterized by the presence of reactive astrocytes and microglia, moderate infiltration of peripheral immune cells, and elevated levels of inflammatory mediators, affects motor regions of the central nervous system (CNS) in sALS and fALS (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Representation of neuroinflammation in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis.

Microglia represent the primary form of active immune defense in the CNS. If these cells cannot eliminate a toxic insult, they remain reactive and continue to recruit astrocytes and oligodendrocytes, causing an ongoing inflammatory process. In ALS patients and animal models, abnormal proliferation of astrocytes (astrogliosis) surrounding the degenerating MNs has been observed. Reactive astrocytes in ALS express inflammatory markers, including cyclooxygenase-2, inducible NOS, and neuronal NOS, as well as inhibitory molecules that block regrowth of a damaged axon (Obrador et al. 2020).

Conclusion

First, a central point in understanding the function of ROS in the brain and in appreciating their therapeutic importance in neuropathology is the multiplicity of ROS-generating mechanisms and the multiplicity of cellular signals activated by them. Second, this multiplicity of ROS-mediated mechanisms suggests that multiple regulations of sources of cellular free radical production should be adopted in devising therapeutic approaches for oxidative stress-mediated neurodegeneration. Third, free radical production by brain tissue cannot be considered only as a by-product of cellular metabolism that becomes dangerous when it escapes control. It is also a central mechanism of regulation for many cellular functions. It is, therefore, advisable that future antioxidant strategies for neurodegeneration be based on mixtures of agents able to modulate multiple mechanisms of free radical production and scavenging without dangerously hampering any essential physiological mechanism based on free radical cellular signaling.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

References

- Aborode AT, Pustake M, Awuah WA, Alwerdani M, Shah P, Yarlagadda R, Ahmad S, Correia IFS, Chandra A, Nansubuga EP, Abdul-Rahman T, Mehta A, Ali O, Amaka SO, Zuñiga YMH, Shkodina AD, Inya OC, Shen B, Alexiou A (2022) Targeting oxidative stress mechanisms to treat Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease: a critical review. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity* 2022(1): e7934442. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7934442>
- Alqahtani T, Deore SL, Kide AK, Shende BA, Sharma R, Chakole RD, Nemade LS, Kale NK, Borah S, Deokar SS, Behera A, Bhandari DD, Gaikwad N, Azad AK, Ghosh A (2023) Mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease, and Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis – an updated review. *Mitochondrion* 71: 83–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mito.2023.05.007>
- AlShimemeri S, Di Luca DG, Fox SH (2021) MPTP Parkinsonism and implications for understanding Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders Clinical Practice* 9(1): 1–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mdc3.13344>
- Amoroso R, Maccallini C, Bellezza I (2023) Activators of Nrf2 to counteract neurodegenerative diseases. *Antioxidants* 12(3): e778. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12030778>
- Andhale R, Shrivastava D (2022) Huntington's disease: a clinical review. *Cureus* 14(8). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.28484>
- Andrés CMC, Perez de la Lastra JM, Juan CA, Plou FJ, Pérez-Lebeña E (2023) Superoxide anion chemistry – its role at the core of the innate immunity. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(3): e1841. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24031841>
- Anwar S, Alrumaihi F, Sarwar T, Babiker AY, Khan AA, Prabhu SV, Rahmani AH (2024) Exploring therapeutic potential of catalase: Strategies in disease prevention and management. *Biomolecules* 14(6): e697. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom14060697>
- Aran KR, Singh S (2023) Mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease – A step towards mitochondria based therapeutic strategies. *Aging and Health Research* 3 (4): e100169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ahr.2023.100169>
- Aranda-Rivera AK, Cruz-Gregorio A, Arancibia-Hernández YL, Hernández-Cruz EY, Pedraza-Chaverri J (2022) RONS and oxidative stress: An overview of basic concepts. *Oxygen* 2(4): 437–478. <https://doi.org/10.3390/oxygen2040030>
- Bagwell E, Larsen J (2024) A review of MPTP-induced parkinsonism in adult zebrafish to explore pharmacological interventions for human Parkinson's disease. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 18: e1451845. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2024.1451845>
- Bai R, Guo J, Ye XY, Xie Y, Xie T (2022) Oxidative stress: The core pathogenesis and mechanism of Alzheimer's disease. *Ageing research reviews* 77: e101619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2022.101619>
- Barberio J, Lally C, Kupelian V, Hardiman O, Flanders WD (2023) Estimated familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis proportion: A literature review and meta-analysis. *Neurology: Genetics* 9(6): e200109. <https://doi.org/10.1212/NXG.0000000000200109>
- Bastioli G, Piccirillo S, Graciotti L, Carone M, Sprega G, Taoussi O, Preziuso A, Castaldo P (2024) Calcium deregulation in neurodegeneration and neuroinflammation in Parkinson's Disease: Role of calcium-storing organelles and sodium-calcium exchanger. *Cells* 13(15): e1301. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells13151301>
- Behrouzi A, Kelley MR, Fehrenbacher JC (2022) Oxidative DNA damage: a role in altering neuronal function. *Journal of cellular signaling* 3(3): e160. <https://doi.org/10.33696/Signaling.3.079>
- Beltrán FA, Troncoso-Escudero P, Villalobos-González J, Mayorga-Weber G, Lara M, Covarrubias-Pinto A, Valdivia S, Vicencio I, Papic E, Paredes-Martínez C, Silva-Januario ME, Rojas A, daSilva LLP, Court F, Rosas-Arellano A, Bátiz LF, Rojas P, Rivera FJ, Castro MA (2025) Distinct roles of ascorbic acid in extracellular vesicles and free form: Implications for metabolism and oxidative stress in presymptomatic Huntington's disease. *Free Radical Biol*

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- ogy and Medicine 227: 521–535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2024.12.001>
- Beura SK, Dhapola R, Panigrahi AR, Yadav P, Reddy DH, Singh SK (2022) Redefining oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease: Targeting platelet reactive oxygen species for novel therapeutic options. *Life Sciences* 306: e120855. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2022.120855>
- Bielski BHJ (1978) Reevaluation of the spectral and kinetic properties of HO₂ and O₂ – free radicals. *Photochemistry and Photobiology* 28 (4–5): 645–649. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-1097.1978.tb06986.x>
- Bin-Jumah MN, Gilani SJ, Alabbasi AF, Al-Abbasi FA, AlGhamdi SA, Alshehri OY, Alghamdi AM, Sayyed N, Kazmi I (2022) Protective effect of fustin against huntington's disease in 3-Nitropropionic treated rats via downregulation of oxidative stress and alteration in neurotransmitters and brain-derived neurotrophic factor activity. *Biomedicines* 10(12): e3021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines10123021>
- Borgstahl GEO, Parge HE, Hickey MJ, Johnson MJ, Boissinot M, Hallewell RA, Lepock JR, Cabelli DE, Tainer JA (1996) Human Mitochondrial Manganese Superoxide Dismutase Polymorphic Variant Ile58Thr Reduces Activity by Destabilizing the Tetrameric Interface. *Biochemistry* 35(14): 4287–4297. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi951892w>
- Brondani M, Roginski AC, Ribeiro RT, de Medeiros MP, Hoffmann CIH, Wajner M, Leipnitz G, Seminotti B (2023) Mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, ER stress and mitochondria-ER crosstalk alternations in a chemical rat model of Huntington's disease: Potential benefits of bezafibrate. *Toxicology letters* 381: 48–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2023.04.011>
- Brookhouser N, Raman S, Frisch C, Srinivasan G, Brafman DA (2021) APOE2 mitigates disease-related phenotypes in an isogenic hi-PSC-based model of Alzheimer's disease. *Molecular psychiatry* 26(10): 5715–5732. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-021-01076-3>
- Brüschweiler S, Fuchs JE, Bader G, McConnell DB, Konrat R, Mayer M (2021) A step toward NRF2-DNA Interaction Inhibitors by Fragment-Based NMR Methods. *ChemMedChem* 16(23): 3576–3587. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cmdc.202100458>
- Buendia I, Michalska P, Navarro E, Gameiro I, Egea J, León R (2016) Nrf2-ARE pathway: an emerging target against oxidative stress and neuroinflammation in neurodegenerative diseases. *Pharmacology & therapeutics* 157: 84–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2015.11.003>
- Buneeva OA, Medvedev AE (2021) DJ-1 protein and its role in the development of Parkinson's disease: studies on experimental models. *Biochemistry* 86(6): 627–640. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S000629792106002X>
- Camiña N, Penning TM (2022) Genetic and epigenetic regulation of the NRF2-KEAP1 pathway in human lung cancer. *British journal of cancer* 126(9): 1244–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41416-021-01642-0>
- Cataldi R, Chia S, Pisani K, Ruggeri FS, Xu CK, Šneideris T, Perni M, Sarwat S, Joshi P, Kumita JR, Linse S, Habchi J, Knowles TPJ, Manini B, Dobson CM, Vendruscolo M (2021) A dopamine metabolite stabilizes neurotoxic amyloid- β oligomers. *Communications Biology* 4(1): 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-020-01490-3>
- Cenini G, Lloret A, Cascella R (2019) Oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases: from a mitochondrial point of view. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/2105607>
- Chakrabarti S, Bisaglia M (2023) Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation in Parkinson's disease: the role of dopamine oxidation products. *Antioxidants* 12(4): e955. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12040955>
- Chianese R, Pierantoni R (2021) Mitochondrial reactive oxygen species (ROS) production alters sperm quality. *Antioxidants* 10(1): e92. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10010092>
- Church FC (2021) Treatment options for motor and non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease. *Biomolecules* 11(4): e612. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11040612>
- Ciftci E, Turkoglu V, Bas Z (2022) Inhibition effect of thymoquinone and lycopene compounds on glutathione reductase enzyme activity purified from human erythrocytes. *Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics* 40(20): 10086–10093. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2021.1939787>
- Contestabile A (2000) Roles of NMDA receptor activity and nitric oxide production in brain development. *Brain Research Reviews* 32(2–3): 476–509. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0173\(00\)00018-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0173(00)00018-7)
- Contestabile A (2001) Oxidative Stress in Neurodegeneration: Mechanisms and Therapeutic Perspectives. *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry* 1(6): 553–568. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568026013394723>
- Copas ANM, McComish SF, Fletcher JM, Caldwell MA (2021) The pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease: a complex interplay between astrocytes, microglia, and T lymphocytes? *Frontiers in neurology* 12: e666737. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2021.666737>
- Cuadrado A (2022) Brain-protective mechanisms of transcription factor NRF2: toward a common strategy for neurodegenerative diseases. *Annual Review of Pharmacology and Toxicology* 62(1): 255–277. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pharmtox-052220-103416>
- Cunha-Oliveira T, Montezinho L, Mendes C, Firuzi O, Saso L, Oliveira PJ, Silva FSG (2020) Oxidative stress in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: pathophysiology and opportunities for pharmacological intervention. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity* 2020(1): e5021694. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5021694>
- Dai C, Tan C, Zhao L, Liang Y, Liu G, Liu H, Zhong Y, Liu Z, Mo L, Liu X, Chen L (2023) Glucose metabolism impairment in Parkinson's disease. *Brain research bulletin* 199: e110672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresbull.2023.110672>
- Decandia D, Gelfo F, Landolfo E, Balsamo F, Petrosini L, Cutuli D (2023) Dietary protection against cognitive impairment, Neuroinflammation and oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease animal models of lipopolysaccharide-induced inflammation. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(6): e5921. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24065921>
- D'Egidio F, Castelli V, Cimini A, d'Angelo M (2023) Cell rearrangement and oxidant/antioxidant imbalance in Huntington's disease. *Antioxidants* 12(3): e571. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12030571>
- Dhapola R, Beura SK, Sharma P, Singh SK, HariKrishnaReddy D (2024) Oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease: current knowledge of signaling pathways and therapeutics. *Molecular biology reports* 51(1): 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-023-09021-z>
- Dionísio PA, Amaral JD, Rodrigues CMP (2021) Oxidative stress and regulated cell death in Parkinson's disease. *Ageing research reviews* 67: e101263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2021.101263>
- Dirx MF, Bologna M (2022) The pathophysiology of Parkinson's disease tremor. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 435: e120196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2022.120196>
- Djordjevic G, Milosevic V, Ljubisavljevic S, Stojanovic I, Stojanov A (2023) Values of nitric oxide and Superoxide dismutase in cerebrospinal fluid of patients with sporadic amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Neurology India* 71(4): 742–747. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0028-3886.383853>

- Domanskyi A, Parlato R (2022) Oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases. *Antioxidants* 11(3): e504. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11030504>
- Dondi A, Carbone C, Manieri E, Zama D, Del Bono C, Betti L, Biagi C, Lanari M (2023) Outdoor air pollution and childhood respiratory disease: the role of oxidative stress. *International journal of molecular sciences* 24(5): e4345. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24054345>
- Dorszewska J, Kowalska M, Prendecki M, Piekut T, Kozłowska J, Kozubski W (2021) Oxidative stress factors in Parkinson's disease. *Neural regeneration research* 16(7): 1383–1391. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1673-5374.300980>
- Duranti E, Villa C (2022) Molecular investigations of protein aggregation in the pathogenesis of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *International journal of molecular sciences* 24(1): e704. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24010704>
- Fahim TM, Mohamed MAE, Abdelrahman SSM, Lotfy DM (2023) Beneficial effect of rosuvastatin therapy on spleen injury induced by gamma irradiation in rats: targeting Nrf2/EPRE pathway. *Dose-Response* 21(2): e15593258231179900. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15593258231179900>
- Fan Y, Maghima M, Chinnathambi A, Alharbi SA, Veeraraghavan VP, Mohan SK, Hussain S, Rengarajan T (2021) Tomentosin reduces behavior deficits and neuroinflammatory response in MPTP-induced Parkinson's disease in mice. *Journal of Environmental Pathology, Toxicology and Oncology* 40(1). <https://doi.org/10.1615/JEnvironPatholToxicolOncol.v40.i1.70>
- Feldman EL, Goutman SA, Petri S, Mazzini L, Savelieff MG, Shaw PJ, Sobue G (2022) Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *The Lancet* 400(10360): 1363–1380. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(22\)01272-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(22)01272-7)
- Flohé L, Toppo S, Orian L (2022) The glutathione peroxidase family: Discoveries and mechanism. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 187: 113–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2022.05.003>
- Fonseca-Ornelas L, Viennet T, Rovere M, Jiang H, Liu L, Nuber S, Ericsson M, Arthanari H, Selkoe DJ (2021) Altered conformation of α -synuclein drives dysfunction of synaptic vesicles in a synaptosomal model of Parkinson's disease. *Cell reports* 36(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2021.109333>
- Freyre EO, Valencia AT, Guzmán DD, Maldonado IC, Ledezma LEB, Carillo MFZ, Escorza MAQ (2021) Oxidative stress as a molecular mechanism of exposure to organophosphorus pesticides: a review. *Current Protein and Peptide Science* 22(12): 890–897. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1389203722666211122092309>
- Gao W, Ning Y, Peng Y, Tang X, Zhong S, Zeng H (2021) LncRNA NKILA relieves astrocyte inflammation and neuronal oxidative stress after cerebral ischemia/reperfusion by inhibiting the NF- κ B pathway. *Molecular immunology* 139: 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molimm.2021.08.002>
- Ghosh S, Ali R, Verma S (2023) A β -oligomers: A potential therapeutic target for Alzheimer's disease. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 239: e124231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.124231>
- Goodman LD, Bellen HJ (2022) Recent insights into the role of glia and oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease gained from *Drosophila*. *Current opinion in neurobiology* 72: 32–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2021.07.012>
- Goutman SA, Hardiman O, Al-Chalabi A, Chió A, Savelieff MG, Kieran MC, Feldman EL (2022) Emerging insights into the complex genetics and pathophysiology of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *The Lancet Neurology* 21(5): 465–479. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(21\)00414-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00414-2)
- Gravandi MM, Abdian S, Tahvilian M, Iranpanah A, Moradi SZ, Fakhri S, Echeverría J (2023) Therapeutic targeting of Ras/Raf/MAPK pathway by natural products: a systematic and mechanistic approach for neurodegeneration. *Phytomedicine* 115: e154821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2023.154821>
- Gupta R, Ambasta RK, Kumar P (2021) Autophagy and apoptosis cascade: which is more prominent in neuronal death? *Cellular and molecular life sciences* 78(24): 8001–8047. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00018-021-04004-4>
- Gupta S, Shukla S (2021) Non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease: opening new avenues in treatment. *Current Research in Behavioral Sciences* 2: e100049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbeha.2021.100049>
- Haber F, Weiss J (1932) Über die katalyse des hydroperoxydes. *Naturwissenschaften* 20(51): 948–950. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01504715>
- Halliwell B (1992) Reactive oxygen species and the central nervous system. *Journal of Neurochemistry* 59(5): 1609–1623. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-4159.1992.tb10990.x>
- Hemerková P, Vališ M (2021) Role of oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: Antioxidant metalloenzymes and therapeutic strategies. *Biomolecules* 11(3): e437. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11030437>
- Hong JY, Oh HH, Park SY, Park YI, Cho SB, Joo YE (2023) Expression of Apurinic/Apyrimidinic Endonuclease 1 in Colorectal Cancer and its Relation to Tumor Progression and Prognosis. *In vivo* 37(5): 2070–2077. <https://doi.org/10.21873/invivo.13304>
- Hosaka T, Tsuji H, Tamaoka A (2021) Biomolecular modifications linked to oxidative stress in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: Determining promising biomarkers related to oxidative stress. *Processes* 9(9): e1667. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9091667>
- Houldsworth A (2024) Role of oxidative stress in neurodegenerative disorders: A review of reactive oxygen species and prevention by antioxidants. *Brain Communications* 6(1): fcad356. <https://doi.org/10.1093/braincomms/fcad356>
- Hua KF, Chao AC, Lin TY, Chen WT, Lee YC, Hsu WH, Lee SL, Wang HM, Yang DI, Ju TC (2022) Ginsenoside compound K reduces the progression of Huntington's disease via the inhibition of oxidative stress and overactivation of the ATM/AMPK pathway. *Journal of Ginseng Research* 46(4): 572–584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgr.2021.11.003>
- Hurben AK, Tretyakova NY (2022) Role of protein damage inflicted by dopamine metabolites in Parkinson's disease: evidence, tools, and outlook. *Chemical research in toxicology* 35(10): 1789–1804. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.2c00193>
- Ibrahim WW, Rasheed NOA (2022) Diapocynin neuroprotective effects in 3-nitropropionic acid Huntington's disease model in rats: emphasis on Sirt1/Nrf2 signaling pathway. *Inflammopharmacology* 30(5): 1745–1758. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10787-022-01004-z>
- Ionescu-Tucker A, Cotman CW (2021) Emerging roles of oxidative stress in brain aging and Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiology of aging* 107: 86–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2021.07.014>
- Islam MR, Jony MH, Thufa GK, Akash S, Dhar PS, Rahman MM, Afroz T, Ahmed M, Hemeg HA, Rauf A, Thiruvengadam M, Venkidasamy B (2024) A clinical study and future prospects for bioactive compounds and semi-synthetic molecules in the therapies for Huntington's disease. *Molecular Neurobiology* 61(3): 1237–1270. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-023-03604-4>

- Ivanov IV, Mappes T, Schaupp P, Lappe C, Wahl S (2018) Ultraviolet radiation oxidative stress affects eye health. *Journal of biophotonics* 11(7): e201700377. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbio.201700377>
- Jarosiewicz B, Morrell M (2021) The RNS System: brain-responsive neurostimulation for the treatment of epilepsy. *Expert review of medical devices* 18(2): 129–138. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17434440.2019.1683445>
- Jarosińska OD, Rüdiger SGD (2021) Molecular strategies to target protein aggregation in Huntington's disease. *Frontiers in molecular biosciences* 8: e769184. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2021.769184>
- Jelinek M, Jurajda M, Duris K (2021) Oxidative stress in the brain: basic concepts and treatment strategies in stroke. *Antioxidants* 10(12): e1886. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10121886>
- Jie Z, Liu J, Shu M, Ying Y, Yang H (2022) Detection strategies for superoxide anion: A review. *Talanta* 236: e122892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2021.122892>
- Jomova K, Alomar SY, Valko R, Liska J, Nepovimova E, Kuca K, Valko M (2025) Flavonoids and their role in oxidative stress, inflammation, and human diseases. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*: e111489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2025.111489>
- Joshi P, Bisht A, Joshi S, Semwal D, Nema NK, Dwivedi J, Sharma S (2022) Ameliorating potential of curcumin and its analogue in central nervous system disorders and related conditions: A review of molecular pathways. *Phytotherapy Research* 36(8): 3143–3180. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.7522>
- Jurcău MC, Andronie-Cioara FL, Jurcău A, Marcu F, Țiț DM, Pașcalău N, Nistor-Cseppentő DC (2022) The link between oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction and neuroinflammation in the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease: therapeutic implications and future perspectives. *Antioxidants* 11(11): e2167. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11112167>
- Kalyanaraman B, Cheng G, Hardy M (2024) Gut microbiome, short-chain fatty acids, alpha-synuclein, neuroinflammation, and ROS/RNS: relevance to Parkinson's disease and therapeutic implications. *Redox Biology* 71: e103092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2024.103092>
- Kohutova A, Münzova D, Pešl M, Rotrekl V (2023) α 1-Adrenoreceptor agonist methoxamine inhibits base excision repair via inhibition of apurinic/apyrimidinic endonuclease I (APE1). *Acta Pharmaceutica* 73(2): 281–291. <https://doi.org/10.2478/acph-2023-0012>
- Konovalova J, Gerasymchuk D, Parkkinen I, Chmielarz P, Domanskyi A (2019) Interplay between MicroRNAs and oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20(23): e6055. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20236055>
- Koppenol WH (2001) The Haber-Weiss cycle – 70 years later. *Redox Report* 6(4): 229–234. <https://doi.org/10.1179/135100001101536373>
- Kostadinova I, Kondeva-Burdina M, Marinov L, Vezekov LL, Simeonova R (2023) Newly synthesized creatine derivatives as potential neuroprotective and antioxidant agents on in vitro models of Parkinson's disease. *Life* 13(1): e139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life13010139>
- Kostrzewa RM (2022) Neonatal 6-hydroxydopamine lesioning of rats and dopaminergic neurotoxicity: Proposed animal model of Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Neural Transmission* 129(5): 445–461. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-022-02479-4>
- Kumaresan M, Khan S (2021) Spectrum of non-motor symptoms in Parkinson's disease. *Cureus* 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.13275>
- Lacerus KV, Kornjakova VV (2022) The role of nitrosative stress in the development of cardiovascular pathology, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, liver pathology and Parkinson's disease. *Scientific Bulletin of the Omsk State Medical University* 2(2): 9–16.
- Latif S, Jahangeer M, Razia DM, Ashiq M, Ghaffar A, Akram M, El Allam A, Bouyahya A, Garipova L, Shariati MA, Thiruvengadam M, Ansari MA (2021) Dopamine in Parkinson's disease. *Clinica chimica acta* 522: 114–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2021.08.009>
- Le Cann K, Foerster A, Rössler C, Erickson A, Hautvast P, Giesselmann S, Pensold D, Kurth I, Rothermel M, Mattis VB, Zimmer-Bensch G, von Hörsten S, Denecke B, Clarner T, Meents J, Lampert A (2021) The difficulty to model Huntington's disease in vitro using striatal medium spiny neurons disseminated from human induced pluripotent stem cells. *Scientific reports* 11(1): e6934. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-85656-x>
- Lebouc M, Bonamy L, Dhellemmes T, Scharnholz J, Richard Q, Courtand G, Brochard A, Martins F, Landry M, Baufrenton J, Garret M (2025) Developmental alterations of indirect-pathway medium spiny neurons in mouse models of Huntington's disease. *Neurobiology of Disease* 208: e106874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2025.106874>
- Leni Z, Künzi L, Geiser M (2020) Air pollution causing oxidative stress. *Current opinion in toxicology* 20: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cotox.2020.02.006>
- Li Y, Zhang JJ, Chen RJ, Chen L, Chen S, Yang XF, Min JW (2022) Genistein mitigates oxidative stress and inflammation by regulating Nrf2/HO-1 and NF- κ B signaling pathways in hypoxic-ischemic brain damage in neonatal mice. *Annals of Translational Medicine* 10(2): 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.21037/atm-21-4958>
- López-Pingarrón L, Almeida H, Soria-Aznar M, Reyes-Gonzales MC, Terrón MP, García JJ (2023) Role of oxidative stress on the etiology and pathophysiology of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and its relation with the enteric nervous system. *Current issues in molecular biology* 45(4): 3315–3332. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cimb45040217>
- Lum PT, Sekar M, Seow LJ, Shaikh MF, Arulsamy A, Retinasamy T, Gan SH, Gnanaaraj C, Esa NM, Ramachawolran G, Subramaniyan V, Chinni SV, Wu YS (2023) Neuroprotective potency of mangiferin against 3-nitropropionic acid induced Huntington's disease-like symptoms in rats: possible antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. *Frontiers in pharmacology* 14: e1189957. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1189957>
- Lv L, Zhang H, Tan J, Wang C (2025) Neuroprotective role and mechanistic insights of DJ-1 dimerization in Parkinson's disease. *Cell Communication and Signaling* 23(1): e129. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12964-025-02136-9>
- Lyngsie G, Krumina L, Tunlid A, Persson P (2018) Generation of hydroxyl radicals from reactions between a dimethoxyhydroquinone and iron oxide nanoparticles. *Scientific Reports* 8(1): e10834. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-29075-5>
- Mahdi WA, AlGhamdi SA, AlGhamdi AM, Imam SS, Alshehri S, Almania MA, Hajjar BM, Al-Abbasi FA, Sayyed N, Kazmi I (2023) Neuroprotectant effects of hibiscetin in 3-nitropropionic acid-induced Huntington's disease via subsiding oxidative stress and modulating monoamine neurotransmitters in rats brain. *Molecules* 28(3): e1402. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28031402>
- Mao R, Zong N, Hu Y, Chen Y, Xu Y (2022) Neuronal death mechanisms and therapeutic strategy in ischemic stroke. *Neuroscience bulletin* 38(10): 1229–1247. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12264-022-00859-0>
- Marí M, Colell A (2021) Mitochondrial oxidative and nitrosative stress as a therapeutic target in diseases. *Antioxidants* 10(2): e314. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10020314>
- Masenga SK, Kabwe LS, Chakulya M, Kirabo A (2023) Mechanisms of oxidative stress in metabolic syndrome. *International journal of molecular sciences* 24(9): e7898. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24097898>

- Medina A, Mahjoub Y, Shaver L, Pringsheim T (2022) Prevalence and incidence of Huntington's disease: an updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *Movement disorders* 37(12): 2327–2335. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.29228>
- Misrani A, Tabassum S, Yang L (2021) Mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease. *Frontiers in aging neuroscience* 13: e617588. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2021.617588>
- Mitoma H, Manto M, Shaikh AG (2021) Mechanisms of ethanol-induced cerebellar ataxia: underpinnings of neuronal death in the cerebellum. *International journal of environmental research and public health* 18(16): e8678. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18168678>
- Mogensen FL, Scafidi A, Poli A, Michelucci A (2023) PARK7/DJ-1 in microglia: implications in Parkinson's disease and relevance as a therapeutic target. *Journal of Neuroinflammation* 20(1): e95. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12974-023-02776-z>
- Moghaddam MH, Bayat AH, Eskandari N, Abdollahifar MA, Fotouhi F, Forouzannia A, Rafiei R, Hatari S, Seraj A, Shahidi AMEJ, Ghorbani Z, Peyvandi AA, Aliaghaei A (2021) Elderberry diet ameliorates motor function and prevents oxidative stress-induced cell death in rat models of Huntington disease. *Brain Research* 1762: e147444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2021.147444>
- Motataianu A, Serban G, Barcutean L, Balasa R (2022) Oxidative stress in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: synergy of genetic and environmental factors. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 23(16): e9339. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23169339>
- Mudway IS, Kelly FJ, Holgate ST (2020) Oxidative stress in air pollution research. *Free Radical Biology & Medicine* 151: 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2020.04.030>
- Mustapha M, Taib CNM (2021) MPTP-induced mouse model of Parkinson's disease: A promising direction for therapeutic strategies. *Bosnian journal of basic medical sciences* 21(4): e422. <https://doi.org/10.17305/bjbms.2020.5181>
- Nagesh R, Kumar KMK, Kumar MN, Patil RH, Sharma SC (2021) Regulation of Jun and Fos AP-1 transcription factors by JNK MAPKs signaling cascade in areca nut extract treated KB cells. *Biochemistry and Biophysics Reports* 27: e101090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrep.2021.101090>
- Naik RA, Mir MN, Malik IA, Bhardwaj R, Alshabrimi FM, Mahmoud MA, Alhomrani M, Alamri AS, Alsanie WF, Hjazzi A, Ghatak T, Poeggeler B, Singh MP, Ts G, Singh SK (2025) The Potential Mechanism and the Role of Antioxidants in Mitigating Oxidative Stress in Alzheimer's disease. *Frontiers in Bioscience-Landmark* 30(2): e25551. <https://doi.org/10.31083/FBL25551>
- Nandi A, Yan LJ, Jana CK, Das N (2019) Role of catalase in oxidative stress – and age-associated degenerative diseases. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9613090>
- Newell ME, Adhikari S, Halden RU (2022) Systematic and state-of-the-science review of the role of environmental factors in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) or Lou Gehrig's Disease. *Science of The Total Environment* 817: e152504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152504>
- Nunes C, Laranjinha J (2021) Nitric oxide and dopamine metabolism converge via mitochondrial dysfunction in the mechanisms of neurodegeneration in Parkinson's disease. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics* 704: e108877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abb.2021.108877>
- Nuskiewicz J, Woźniak A, Szewczyk-Golec K (2020) Ionizing radiation as a source of oxidative stress – the protective role of melatonin and vitamin D. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 21(16): e5804. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21165804>
- Obrador E, Salvador R, López-Blanch R, Jihad-Jebbar A, Vallés SL, Estrella JM (2020) Oxidative stress, neuroinflammation and mitochondria in the pathophysiology of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Antioxidants* 9(9): e901. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9090901>
- Okoye CN, Koren SA, Wojtovich AP (2023) Mitochondrial complex I ROS production and redox signaling in hypoxia. *Redox biology* 67: e102926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2023.102926>
- Oliveira TT, Coutinho LG, de Oliveira LOA, Timoteo ARS, Farias GC, Agnez-Lima LF (2022) APE1/Ref-1 role in inflammation and immune response. *Frontiers in Immunology* 13: e793096. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2022.793096>
- Orobets KS, Karamyshev AL (2023) Amyloid precursor protein and Alzheimer's disease. *International journal of molecular sciences* 24(19): e14794. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241914794>
- Pagonabarraga J, Tinazzi M, Caccia C, Jost WH (2021) The role of glutamatergic neurotransmission in the motor and non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease: clinical cases and a review of the literature. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience* 90: 178–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2021.05.056>
- Paithankar JG, Saini S, Dwivedi S, Sharma A, Chowdhuri DK (2021) Heavy metal associated health hazards: An interplay of oxidative stress and signal transduction. *Chemosphere* 262: e128350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128350>
- Palma FR, Gantner BN, Sakiyama MJ, Kayzuka C, Shukla S, Lacchini R, Cunniff B, Bonini MG (2024) ROS production by mitochondria: Function or dysfunction? *Oncogene* 43(5): 295–303. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41388-023-02907-z>
- Panes JD, Wendt A, Ramirez-Molina O, Castro PA, Fuentealba J (2022) Deciphering the role of PGC-1 α in neurological disorders: from mitochondrial dysfunction to synaptic failure. *Neural regeneration research* 17(2): 237–245. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1673-5374.317957>
- Pei J, Pan X, Wei G, Hua Y (2023) Research progress of glutathione peroxidase family (GPX) in redoxiation. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 14: e1147414. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1147414>
- Pogoda A, Chmielewska N, Maciejak P, Szyndler J (2021) Transcriptional dysregulation in Huntington's disease: the role in pathogenesis and potency for pharmacological targeting. *Current medicinal chemistry* 28(14): 2783–2806. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867327666200705225821>
- Pranty AI, Szeapanowski LP, Wruck W, Karikari AA, Adjaye J (2024) Hemozoin induces malaria via activation of DNA damage, p38 MAPK and neurodegenerative pathways in a human iPSC-derived neuronal model of cerebral malaria. *Scientific Reports* 14(1): e24959. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-76259-3>
- Prates-Rodrigues M, Schweizer BLA, Gomes CP, Ribeiro AM, Padovan-Neto FE, Masini D, Lopes-Aguilar C (2025) Challenges and Opportunities in Exploring Non-Motor Symptoms in 6-Hydroxydopamine Models of Parkinson's disease: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Neurochemistry* 169(2): e70008. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnc.70008>
- Pyatha S, Kim H, Lee D, Kim K (2022) Association between heavy metal exposure and Parkinson's disease: a review of the mechanisms related to oxidative stress. *Antioxidants* 11(12): e2467. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11122467>
- Raber J, Stagaman K, Kasschau KD, Davenport C, Lopes L, Nguyen D, Torres ER, Sharpton TJ, Kisby G (2023) Behavioral and cognitive performance following exposure to Second-Hand Smoke (SHS) from tobacco products associated with Oxidative-Stress-Induced DNA damage and repair and disruption of the gut microbiome. *Genes* 14(9): e1702. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes14091702>

- Rekatsina M, Paladini A, Piroli A, Zis P, Pergolizzi JV, Varrassi G (2020) Pathophysiology and therapeutic perspectives of oxidative stress and neurodegenerative diseases: a narrative review. *Advances in Therapy* 37: 113–139. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12325-019-01148-5>
- Ren Q, Bakker W, de Haan L, Rietjens IMCM, Bouwmeester H (2023) Induction of Nrf2-EPRE-mediated gene expression by hydroxyanthraquinones present in extracts from traditional Chinese medicine and herbs. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 176: e113802. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2023.113802>
- Rios-Covian D, Butcher LD, Ablack AL, den Hartog G, Matsubara MT, Ly H, Oates AW, Xu G, Fisch KM, Ahrens ET, Toden S, Brown CC, Kim K, Le D, Eckmann L, Dhar B, Izumi T, Ernst PB, Crowe SE (2023) A Novel Hypomorphic Apex1 Mouse Model Implicates Apurinic/Apyrimidinic Endonuclease 1 in Oxidative DNA Damage Repair in Gastric Epithelial Cells. *Antioxidants & Redox Signalling* 38(1–3): 183–197. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2021.0119>
- Roda AR, Serra-Mir G, Montoliu-Gaya L, Tiessler L, Villegas S (2022) Amyloid-beta peptide and tau protein crosstalk in Alzheimer's disease. *Neural regeneration research* 17(8): 1666–1674. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1673-5374.332127>
- Rosa AC, Corsi D, Cavi N, Bruni N, Dosio F (2021) Superoxide dismutase administration: A review of proposed human uses. *Molecules* 26(7): e1844. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26071844>
- Saha S, Buttari B, Profumo E, Tucci P, Saso L (2022) A perspective on Nrf2 signaling pathway for neuroinflammation: a potential therapeutic target in Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease. *Frontiers in cellular neuroscience* 15: e787258. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2021.787258>
- Samarakoon T, Fujino T, Hagimori M, Saito R (2023) Cadmium uptake and oxidative-stress-induced DNA alternations in the freshwater cladoceran *Moina macrocopa* (Straus 1820) following consecutive short-term exposure assessments. *Limnology* 24(1): 9–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10201-022-00702-5>
- Sap KA, Geijtenbeek KW, Schipper-Krom S, Guler AT, Reits EA (2023) Ubiquitin-modifying enzymes in Huntington's disease. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences* 10: e1107323. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2023.1107323>
- Sawant N, Morton H, Kshirsagar S, Reddy AP, Reddy PH (2021) Mitochondrial abnormalities and synaptic damage in Huntington's disease: a focus on defective mitophagy and mitochondria-targeted therapeutics. *Molecular Neurobiology*: 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-021-02556-x>
- Shahim P, Norato G, Sinaï N, Zetterberg H, Blennow K, Chan L, Grunseich C (2024) Neurofilaments in sporadic and familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Genes* 15(4): e496. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes15040496>
- Sharma C, Kim SR (2021) Linking oxidative stress and proteinopathy in Alzheimer's disease. *Antioxidants* 10(8): e1231. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10081231>
- Sharma P, Kumar M, Bansal N (2021) Ellagic acid prevents 3-nitropropionic acid induced symptoms of Huntington's disease. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Archives of Pharmacology* 394(9): 1917–1928. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-021-02106-1>
- Shibata N, Kataoka I, Okamura Y, Murakami K, Kato Y, Yamamoto T, Masui K (2025) Implications for soluble iron accumulation, oxidative stress, and glial glutamate release in motor neuron death associated with sporadic amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Neuropathology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/neup.13033>
- Siñes-Bailo P, Martín EL, Calmarza P, Brea SM, Gómez AB, Giráldez AP, Callau JJS, Santamaría JMV, Khialani AD, Micó CC, Andreu JC, Tormo GS, Gallifa IF (2022) The role of oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases and potential antioxidant therapies. *Advances in Laboratory Medicine* 3(4): 342–350. <https://doi.org/10.1515/almed-2022-0111>
- Singh A, Kukreti R, Saso L, Kukreti S (2019) Oxidative stress: a key modulator in neurodegenerative diseases. *Molecules* 24(8): e1583. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24081583>
- Singh A, Upadhyay S, Mehan S (2021) Understanding abnormal c-JNK/p38MAPK signaling overactivation involved in the progression of multiple sclerosis: possible therapeutic targets and impact on neurodegenerative diseases. *Neurotoxicity Research* 39(5): 1630–1650. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12640-021-00401-6>
- Skou LD, Johansen SK, Okarmus J, Meyer M (2024) Pathogenesis of DJ-1/PARK7-mediated Parkinson's disease. *Cells* 13(4): e296. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells13040296>
- Sanghai N, Tranmer GK (2021) Hydrogen peroxide and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: from biochemistry to pathophysiology. *Antioxidants* 11(1): 1–52. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11010052>
- Sies H, Belousov VV, Chandel NS, Davies MJ, Jones DP, Mann GE, Murphy MP, Yamamoto M, Winterbourn C (2022) Defining roles of specific reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cell biology and physiology. *Nature reviews Molecular cell biology* 23(7): 499–515. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41580-022-00456-z>
- Sies H, Jones DP (2020) Reactive oxygen species (ROS) as pleiotropic physiological signalling agents. *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology* 21(7): 363–383. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41580-020-0230-3>
- Suzen S, Tucci P, Profumo E, Buttari B, Saso L (2022) A pivotal role of Nrf2 in neurodegenerative disorders: a new way for therapeutic strategies. *Pharmaceuticals* 15(6): e692. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15060692>
- Tabrizi SJ, Schobel S, Gantman EC, Mansbach A, Borowsky B, Konstantinova P, Mestre TA, Panagoulas J, Ross CA, Zauderer M, Mullin AP, Romero K, Sivakumaran S, Turner EC, Long JD, Sampaio C (2022) A biological classification of Huntington's disease: the Integrating Staging System. *The Lancet Neurology* 21(7): 632–644. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(22\)00120-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(22)00120-X)
- Takahashi S, Mashima K (2022) Neuroprotection and disease modification by astrocytes and microglia in Parkinson disease. *Antioxidants* 11(1): e170. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11010170>
- Tchekalarova J, Tzoneva R (2023) Oxidative stress and aging as risk factors for Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease: the role of the antioxidant melatonin. *International journal of molecular sciences* 24(3): e3022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24033022>
- Teleanu DM, Niculescu AG, Lungu II, Radu CI, Vladăncenco O, Roza E, Costăchescu B, Grumezescu AM, Teleanu RI (2022) An overview of oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and neurodegenerative diseases. *International journal of molecular sciences* 23(11): e5938. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23115938>
- Tripodi G, Lombardo M, Kerav S, Aiello G, Baldelli S (2025) Nitric Oxide in Parkinson's Disease: The Potential Role of Dietary Nitrate in Enhancing Cognitive and Motor Health via the Nitrate-Nitrite-Nitric Oxide Pathway. *Nutrients* 17(3): e393. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu17030393>
- Tsai KC, Chen CS, Su JH, Lee YC, Tseng YH, Wei WC (2023) The blockade of Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase 14 activation by marine natural product Crassolide triggers ICD in tumor cells and stimulates anti-tumor immunity. *Marine Drugs* 21(4): e225. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md21040225>

- Urano A, Yamamoto M (2023) The KEAP1-NRF2 system and neurodegenerative diseases. *Antioxidants & redox signaling* 38(13): 974–988. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2023.0234>
- Vastegani SM, Nasrolahi A, Ghaderi S, Belali R, Rashno M, Farzaneh M, Khoshnam SE (2023) Mitochondrial dysfunction and Parkinson's disease: pathogenesis and therapeutic strategies. *Neurochemical research* 48(8): 2285–2308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11064-023-03904-0>
- Wang H, Zeng R (2024) Aberrant protein aggregation in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Journal of Neurology* 271(8): 4826–4851. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-024-12485-z>
- Wang Z, Wang X, Li X, Lu K, Wang L, Ma X, Song K, Zhang C (2024) Antioxidant effects of the aqueous extract of turmeric against hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative stress in spotted seabass (*Lateolabrax maculatus*). *Aquaculture and Fisheries* 9(1): 71–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaf.2022.11.003>
- Weaver K, Skouta R (2022) The selenoprotein glutathione peroxidase 4: from molecular mechanisms to novel therapeutic opportunities. *Biomedicines* 10(4): e891. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines10040891>
- Wu H, Liu Q, Yang N, Xu S (2023) Polystyrene-microplastics and DEHP co-exposure induced DNA damage, cell cycle arrest and necroptosis of ovarian granulosa cells in mice by promoting ROS production. *Science of the Total Environment* 871: e161962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161962>
- Xu H, Yang F (2022) The interplay of dopamine metabolism abnormalities and mitochondrial defects in the pathogenesis of schizophrenia. *Translational psychiatry* 12(1): e464. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-022-02233-0>
- Yan L, Li L, Lei J (2021) Long noncoding RNA small nucleolar RNA host gene 12/microRNA-138-5p/nuclear factor I/B regulates neuronal apoptosis, inflammatory response, and oxidative stress in Parkinson's disease. *Bioengineered* 12(2): 12867–12879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21655979.2021.2005928>
- Yang Y, Bagyinszky E, An SSA (2023) Presenilin-1 (PSEN1) mutations: clinical phenotypes beyond Alzheimer's disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(9): e8417. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24098417>
- Younus H (2018) Therapeutic potentials of superoxide dismutase. *International Journal of Health Sciences* 12(3): 88–93.
- Yuan HH, Yin H, Marincas M, Xie LL, Bu LL, Guo MH, Zheng XL (2025) From DNA Repair to Redox Signaling: The Multifaceted Role of APEX1 (Apurinic/Apyrimidinic Endonuclease 1) in Cardiovascular Health and Disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 26(7): e3034. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26073034>
- Zgorzynska E, Dziedzic B, Walczewska A (2021) An overview of the Nrf2/ARE pathway and its role in neurodegenerative diseases. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22(17): e9592. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22179592>
- Zhang L, Wang X, Cueto R, Effi C, Zhang Y, Tan H, Qin X, Ji Y, Yang X, Wang H (2019) Biochemical basis and metabolic interplay of redox regulation. *Redox Biology* 26: e101284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2019.101284>
- Zhang R, Xiao N, Xu Q, Gong Q, Kong F, Jiang H (2023) Pleiotropic effects of a mitochondrion-targeted glutathione reductase inhibitor on restraining tumor cells. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 248: e115069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2022.115069>
- Zhang T, Dong Z, Liu F, Pan E, He N, Ma F, Wang G, Wang Y, Dong J (2022) Avermectin induces carp neurotoxicity by mediating blood-brain barrier dysfunction, oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis through PI3K/Akt and NF- κ B pathways. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 243: e113961. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2022.113961>
- Zhao Z (2023) Hydroxyl radical generations form the physiologically relevant Fenton-like reactions. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 208: 510–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2023.09.013>
- Zheng M, Liu Y, Zhang G, Yang Z, Xu W, Chen Q (2023) The applications and mechanisms of superoxide dismutase in medicine, food, and cosmetics. *Antioxidants* 12(9): e1675. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12091675>